

ISic1350

I.Sicily inscription 1350

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Chiesa del Carmine

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140852

1. Βονιφα (τίου) □ μνημῖον.
2. ἡ τῶν πολ (λ) ὦν θλίψεων ὑπωμονή ἐλπίδα
3. σωτηρίας κατεργάζετε· πᾶσιν οὖν ἡμῖν τοῖς πο-
4. θοῦσιν ζωῆς αἰωνίου τυχῖν προσκίσθω καὶ ἡ τῆς
5. ὑπομονῆς πρᾶξις, δι' ἧς κ (αἰ) πολλοὶ ζωῆς οὐρανίου ἔτυχον·
6. ὅθεν κά[γ]ῶ ὁ πάμπαν ἀμαρτωλὸς ἠύξάμην τοῦ βίου
7. τούτου τὴν παροικίαν [τ]ά[χ]ιον ἐκφυγῖν κ (αἰ) γε εὐξά-
8. μενος τούτου ἔτυχον μ[ετ]ὰ τὴν ἐκ τοῦ βίου ἐπὶ τὴν
9. δικαιοσύνην μεταβολήν· ἀπὸ παντὸς τοίνυν τοῦ
10. ἀνεσθήτου βίου ἡ [κ]οίμα[σις] δοθήτω μετὰ τῆς ἐν Χρ (ιστ) ῶ
11. συνδούλης μου κ (αἰ) τῆς [γ]λυ[κυ]τάτης μου μητρός. □
- 12.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492963

EDCS 39101728

PHI 140852

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-22): ISic1350. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4385826>